

Assessing LSST's ability to hunt LIGO black holes with microlensing

Natasha S. Abrams

Advised by Prof. Christopher Stubbs (Harvard University) and Prof. Masahiro Takada (Kavli Institute for the Physics and Mathematics of the Universe, University of Tokyo)

1. Abstract

Gravitational microlensing is a powerful tool to study invisible objects, such as black holes, in the Milky Way. By monitoring highly populated areas like the Galactic bulge region, one can observe microlensing events due to brown dwarfs, main-sequence stars, white dwarfs, neutron stars, and black holes. We model the microlensing event rates with source stars in the Galactic bulge region using standard spatial and velocity distributions of stars in the Galactic bulge and disk. We find that if black holes have an extended Salpeter-like mass function (as indicated by the recent LIGO binary-black hole gravitational wave events) and a similar velocity and spatial structure to stars, the black hole population leads to a distinct increase in the microlensing event rate with Einstein crossing time on the order of 100 days. By looking toward the Galactic bulge region and observing on the order of 10^8 stars, we could potentially observe this excess of microlensing events. The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) holds the potential to make these observations. We evaluate the efficacy of potential LSST cadences for both triggering and characterizing the light curves of black hole microlensing. For three candidate LSST observing cadences, we find that a deterministic scanning of the sky (the altLike cadence) detects and triggers a higher percentage of microlensing events than the greedy-optimized cadence weighted toward the Galactic bulge region, and both do better than LSST's baseline cadence, though there is little difference at high Einstein crossing times.

2. Introduction

Gravitational lensing is when a mass, such as a black hole or star, acts as a lens and bends the light of a background star, magnifying it and often creating multiple images. Microlensing is the manifestation of this phenomenon in which multiple images are not resolved due to the limited angular resolution of the telescope, but one can instead see an increase in the observed flux of the source star varying as a function of time. Since one does not need to see the lens in order to measure its effects, it is a powerful tool to measure invisible objects such as dark matter (as was the goal of MACHO (Alcock et al. 2000 [1]) and EROS (Tisserand et al. 2007 [2]) projects) or black holes. Here we study how the future observation of microlensing events may affect our understanding of the stellar black hole mass function.

The approach adopted here for modeling the microlensing event rates is based on the methodology in Niikura et al. 2019 [3] which focused primarily on the events caused by low mass objects on the scale $10^{-6}M_{\odot}$. This

paper focuses on black holes in the mass range that LIGO has found.

The upcoming Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) has the potential sensitivity to observe these events and the community is currently evaluating various cadences to optimize the use of the telescope. In this paper, we evaluate the effectiveness of observing microlensing events caused by stellar black holes for the three candidate LSST observing cadences.

3. Methodology

The amplification (A) of the source is a function of the impact parameter u (distance between lens and line of sight between observer and the source scaled to the Einstein radius ($u = \frac{r(t)}{R_e}$)) which changes as the lens moves across the sky. The Einstein radius is defined as $\frac{\sqrt{4GMd_l d_{ls}/d_s}}{c}$ where d_l is the distance from the observer to the lens, d_s is the distance from the observer to the source, and d_{ls} is the distance between the lens and the source. So the amplification is

$$A = \frac{u^2 + 2}{u\sqrt{u^2 + 4}} \quad (1)$$

where u is a function of t

$$u(t) = \sqrt{u_{min}^2 + \frac{(t - t_0)^2}{t_e^2}}. \quad (2)$$

Here, t_0 is the time where the two objects are closest on the sky and t_e is the Einstein crossing time (the time over which the source is amplified), which is the Einstein radius (the radius at which the Einstein ring would appear if it could be resolved) divided by the lens's perpendicular velocity.

$$t_e = \frac{R_e}{v_{\perp}} = \frac{\sqrt{4GMd_l d_{ls}/d_s}}{cv_{\perp}} \quad (3)$$

where c is the speed of light.

There is a tube between the observer and the source created by the volume within which objects would produce an amplification greater than $A(u = 1) = 1.34$. We can find the microlensing event rate by integrating over the number of objects passing through the tube with a particular velocity. See Niikura et al [3] for a more in-depth derivation. The rate of microlensing events with lenses in the bulge is

$$\frac{d\Gamma_b}{dt_e} = \frac{\pi}{N_s} \int_{d_s, min}^{d_s, max} dd_s n_s(d_s) \sum_i \int_{d_s, min}^{d_s} dd_l \frac{\rho_{b,i}(d_l)}{M_i} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} d\theta v_{\perp}^4 f_{b,i}(v_{\perp}, \theta) \quad (4)$$

where i represents the various components (main sequence stars, brown dwarfs, white dwarfs, neutron stars, and black holes), $N_s = \int_{d_s, min}^{d_s, max} dd_s n_s(d_s)$, n_s is the number distribution of objects in the bulge, $d_{s, min} = 4$

kpc, $d_{s,max} = 12$ kpc (since the center of the bulge is approximately 8 kpc away with a radius of approximately 4 kpc), $\rho_{b,i}$ are the mass distributions in the bulge, $v_{\perp} = \frac{2R_e \cos(\theta)}{t_e}$, and $f_{b,i}(v_{\perp}, \theta)$ are transverse velocity distributions in the bulge. Similarly, the event rate of microlensing events with lenses in the disk is

$$\frac{d\Gamma_d}{dt_e} = \pi \sum_i \int_0^{\bar{d}_s} dd_l \frac{\rho_{d,i}(d_l)}{M_i} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} d\theta v_{\perp}^4 f_{d,i}(v_{\perp}, \theta) \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{d}_s = 8$ kpc. The factor in front is different since in the disk calculation we assume the objects in the bulge (our objects being lensed) are all approximately in the same place. Whereas, when objects in the bulge region are being lensed by objects in the bulge we must weight by the number distribution in the bulge.

It was assumed that the mass and velocity distributions only depended on location (bulge, disk, etc.) and not on the stellar component. We used the bulge mass distribution described in Kent (1992) [4]

$$\rho_b(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} 1.04 \times 10^6 \left(\frac{s}{0.482 pc}\right)^{-1.85} M_{\odot}/pc^3 & s < 938 pc \\ 3.53 K_0\left(\frac{s}{667 pc}\right) M_{\odot}/pc^3 & s \geq 938 pc \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where K_0 is the modified Bessel function of zeroth order of the second kind and $s^4 = R^4 + (z/0.61)^4$, $R^2 = x^2 + y^2$, $x = d_l \cos(b) \cos(l)$, $y = d_l \cos(b) \sin(l)$, and $z = d_l \sin(b)$ where d_l is in parsecs and (l, b) are the Galactic coordinates. The disk mass distribution described in Bahcall (1986) [5] is

$$\rho_d(x, y, z) = 0.06 \times \exp \left[- \left(\frac{R - 8000}{3500} + \frac{|z|}{350} \right) \right] M_{\odot}/pc^3. \quad (7)$$

For the velocity we assumed Gaussian distributions with independent y and z velocities from Han and Gould (1995) [6]. For the bulge y -direction we assumed $\mu = -220(1-\alpha)$ km/s and $\sigma = \sqrt{1 + \alpha^2} 100$ km/s, for the bulge z -direction $\mu = 0$ km/s $\sigma = \sqrt{1 + \alpha^2} 100$ km/s, for the disk y -direction $\mu = 220\alpha$ km/s and $\sigma = \sqrt{(\kappa\delta + 30)^2 + (100\alpha)^2}$ km/s, and for the z -direction $\mu = 0$ km/s and $\sigma = \sqrt{(\kappa\delta + 30)^2 + (100\alpha)^2}$ km/s, where $\alpha \equiv d_l/d_s$, $\kappa \equiv 5.625 \times 10^3$ km/s/pc, $\lambda \equiv 3.75 \times 10^3$ km/s/pc, and $\delta \equiv (8000x)$ pc.

To do the event rate integral, one must know the distribution of the various stellar components. For the initial mass functions of these components, a modified version of Kroupa's IMF [7] was used:

$$\frac{dn_s(M)}{d \ln M} = \begin{cases} A_{BD} (M/0.08 M_{\odot})^{1-\alpha_{BD}}, & (0.01 \leq M/M_{\odot} \leq 0.08) \\ A_{MS} (M/0.5 M_{\odot})^{1-\alpha_{MS1}}, & (0.08 \leq M/M_{\odot} \leq 0.5) \\ A_{MS} (M/0.5 M_{\odot})^{1-\alpha_{MS2}}, & (0.5 \leq M/M_{\odot} \leq 100), \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where BDs are brown dwarfs, and MS1 and MS2 are low and high mass main sequence stars, respectively. α_{BD} is 0.8, α_{MS1} is 1.3, and α_{MS2} is 2. In theory, high mass main sequence stars can be more massive than $100 M_{\odot}$, but there are not very many (if any) stars known to have a higher mass. We assume that stars between $1 M_{\odot}$ and $8 M_{\odot}$ evolve to white dwarfs, between $8 M_{\odot}$ and $20 M_{\odot}$ to neutron stars, and between $20 M_{\odot}$ and $100 M_{\odot}$ to black holes. White dwarfs are assumed to evolve according to the following mass relation:

$$M_{WD} = 0.339 + 0.129M_{MS} \quad (9)$$

$$dM_{WD} = 0.129dM_{MS}. \quad (10)$$

The white dwarf mass function can be found by equating the number density of white dwarfs with the number density of main sequence stars in the mass range where we assume all the main sequence stars evolve to white dwarfs.

$$n_{WD} = n_{MS} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dn_{WD}}{dlnM_{WD}} dlnM_{WD} = \frac{dn_{MS}}{dlnM_{MS}} dlnM_{MS} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{dn_{WD}}{dlnM_{WD}} = A_{MS} \left(\frac{M_{MS}}{0.5M_{\odot}} \right)^{1-2} \frac{dlnM_{MS}}{dlnM_{WD}} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dn_{WD}}{dlnM_{WD}} = A_{MS} \left[\frac{M_{WD} - 0.339}{0.5M_{\odot}} \right]^{-1} \frac{M_{WD}}{M_{WD} - 0.339}. \quad (14)$$

Niikura et al. [3] assumed a simple Gaussian mass model for neutron stars and black holes. This relation was kept for neutron stars, but for black holes an extended Salpeter-like function (as indicated by the recent LIGO binary-black hole gravitational wave events) was used (Abbott et al. 2009 [8]).

$$\frac{dn_{NS}}{dM_{NS}} = \frac{A_{NS}}{\sqrt{2\pi}(0.12 M_{\odot})^2} e^{-\frac{(M_{NS}-1.33 M_{\odot})^2}{2(0.12 M_{\odot})^2}} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{dn_{BH}}{dlnM_{BH}} = A_{BH} \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^{-1}. \quad (16)$$

In Figure 1, which plots these mass functions, since the y axis is $\frac{dn}{dlnM}$, the neutron star curve is multiplied by an additional factor of M. The black hole mass function is broken up into 9 bins. The overall normalization of this plot is arbitrary since we have not yet specified A_{MS} . A_{MS} was set equal to 1, the brown dwarfs were normalized so the IMFs are continuous, and the remnants were normalized based on conservation of number

(since we assume all the high mass main sequence stars evolve). For example:

$$\text{White Dwarf Normalization} = \frac{\int_{1M_{\odot}}^{8M_{\odot}} d\ln M A_{MS} \left(\frac{M}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right)^{1-\alpha_{MS2}}}{\int_{0.339+0.129(1M_{\odot})}^{0.339+0.129(8M_{\odot})} d\ln M A_{MS} \left[\frac{M_{WD}-0.339}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right]^{-1} \frac{M_{WD}}{M_{WD}-0.339}} \quad (17)$$

Figure 1. Plotted here is $\log\left(\frac{dn}{d\ln M}\right)$ (mass distribution) vs $\log(M (M_{\odot}))$. The normalization on the y-axis is arbitrary. The brown dwarf, low mass main sequence, and high mass main sequence are assumed to have Kroupa-like initial mass function. The high mass main sequence stars of the appropriate masses are assumed to have evolved into white dwarfs (shaded in red), neutron stars (shaded in purple), and black holes (shaded in grey).

The white dwarf mass function was found by number conservation, the neutron stars are assumed to have a Gaussian distribution, and black holes to have a Salpeter-like mass function as indicated by LIGO.

The value of A_{MS} (the normalization) was found by performing the following integral:

$$\rho_* = \int_{0.08M_{\odot}}^{M_{\odot}} d\ln M M \frac{dn}{d\ln M} \quad (18)$$

$$= \int_{0.08M_{\odot}}^{0.5M_{\odot}} \frac{dM}{M} M A_{MS} \left(\frac{M}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right)^{1-1.3} + \int_{0.5M_{\odot}}^{M_{\odot}} \frac{dM}{M} M A_{MS} \left(\frac{M}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right)^{1-2} \quad (19)$$

$$= A_{MS} \left[\int_{0.08M_{\odot}}^{0.5M_{\odot}} dM \left(\frac{M}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right)^{-0.3} + \int_{0.5M_{\odot}}^{M_{\odot}} dM \left(\frac{M}{0.5M_{\odot}}\right)^{-1} \right] \quad (20)$$

$$= A_{MS} \left[\frac{1}{(0.5M_{\odot})^{-0.3}} \frac{0.5^{0.7} - 0.08^{0.7}}{0.7} - \frac{\ln(0.5)}{(0.5M_{\odot})^{-1}} \right] \quad (21)$$

$$= A_{ms}(0.86) \quad (22)$$

Here ρ_* is the numerical constant in front of the stellar density of various components of the Galaxy (disk, inner bulge, and outer bulge). For example, in the disk ρ_* is $0.06 M_{\odot}/pc^3$ from equation (7). Note that

$\exp[-(R - 8000)/3500 + z/325]$ and the other equivalent unitless formulas will be called $g_i(x,y,z)$. So, to find A_{MS} for the disk, we divide 0.06 by 0.86 and find $A_{MS} \approx 0.06981/pc^3$.

Equations (4) and (5) were renormalized and instead of summing over the masses, they were integrated over, weighting by the mass function. Also, instead of integrating over the mass density and dividing by M, the expression in units of number density was used, which was obtained by finding $A_{MS}g_i(x,y,z)$.

So for the disk

$$\frac{d\Gamma_d}{dt_e} = \pi \int_0^{\bar{d}_s} dd_l g_d(x, y, z) \int_{M_{low}}^{M_{high}} \frac{dn}{dlnM} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} d\theta v_{\perp}^4 f_d(v_{\perp}, \theta). \tag{23}$$

Binary stars were taken into account by doubling the lower and upper mass bounds and halving the result of the integral. In theory, the microlensing effects of binary systems changes based on the separation of the objects, but the simplifying assumption that they are close enough together to be treated as one star was made. The binary stars accounted for 40% of the systems.

Three LSST cadences were evaluated: the baseline_v1.3_10yrs cadence, which is an algorithmically determined cadence with a few deep drilling spots; the bulges_cadence_bulge_wfdv1.3_10yrs cadence, which is a similarly algorithmically determined cadence with a focus on the Galactic bulge; and the altLike_v1.3_10yrs cadence, which is a deterministic cadence that scans the meridian as the sky as it passes overhead. The simulated cadences are from the OpSim database [9], [10] made by the LSST team, which take into account historical weather conditions and other variables. Figure 2 shows the intervals between observations from 100 days to 400 days, where each dot is an observation. Figure 3 shows the interval between observations for the entire 10 year survey. The gaps are when the bulge is not visible in the sky.

Figure 2. Cadences vs time (days) between 100 and 400 days. At this scale, one can see that the cadences differ.

The altLike cadence has 730 observations in this range, bulge has 545, and baseline has 261.

Figure 3. Cadences vs time (days) for the eight fields described above for the entire 10 year survey with gaps indicating where the bulge is not visible. The y-axis is arbitrary to distinguish between the cadences.

We extracted data from eight fields around the bulge ($270^\circ, -30^\circ$) each ranging 3.5° in RA and Dec around the center of the field of view to correspond to LSST’s field of view. The center of each field of view is 4° apart so they do not overlap. See Figure 4 for the coordinates of the center of each field and the center of the set of fields.

Figure 4. Eight fields of view around the Galactic bulge region. Each field of view ranges 3.5° in RA and Dec around the center of the field of view. The center of each field of view is 4° apart so they do not overlap.

To evaluate the cadences, 10,800 lightcurves were simulated with various t_e , t_0 , and u_{min} . Ten values of t_e logarithmically spaced between 0 and 2000 days were chosen; the upper bound is due to the event rate dropping off at around this value (see Figure 5). The 120 values of t_0 were chosen spaced evenly for the 10 year survey, so there is one month between each value. Ten values of u_{min} were chosen, evenly spaced from 0 to 1. These lightcurves were then sampled with the simulated cadences.

The various LSST cadences were evaluated under two metrics: how well they could trigger and how well they could characterize microlensing events. An event would be “triggered” if there were at least two observations of the lightcurve with at least a 10% amplification. An event was considered “detected” with $A \geq 1.1$ and at least four observations on either side of the peak. This ensured that it was observed at least two nights before and after the amplification peak since often two observations will be taken on one night.

4. Results

In Figure 5, $\frac{d\Gamma_d}{dt_e} + \frac{d\Gamma_b}{dt_e}$ is multiplied by the efficiency, by t_e , and by 5 years in units of seconds. 5 years is the duration of observation of OGLE, the microlensing survey studied in Niikura et al. 2019 [3] and was chosen here to follow the procedure of that paper. This is the event rate per star per 5 years. So, by multiplying by the number of stars, we find number of expected events per 5 years.

Figure 5. Plotted here is $\log(\frac{dN}{dlnt_e})$ vs $\log(t_e$ (days)). If one multiplies $\frac{dN}{dlnt_e}$ by the number of stars, one finds the event rate/5 years. The green curve shows the summation of the event rates, and there it is evident that there is a hump in the total around $t_e \approx$ one year caused by the black hole contribution.

It is evident that there is a hump in the total around $t_e \approx$ one year caused by the black hole contribution. Integrating over all events at $t_e >$ one year, there are 3.28 times as many events caused by black holes as by main sequence stars, white dwarfs, and neutron stars combined.

By plotting the trigger efficiency (see Figure 6) and detection efficiency (see Figure 7) as a function of t_e , we can see that the altLike cadence detects the highest percentage of light curves, the bulge cadence detects the second highest, and the baseline cadence detects the lowest. At high Einstein crossing times (over 100 days), there is no real difference between the cadences. At maximum efficiency, they are being triggered on all events and detecting nearly all. It is likely that the cadences do not detect all of the events due to some

of the events having their peak extremely close to when the cadences begin or end their observations, so the telescope is unable to make four observations before and after the peak for those events.

Figure 6. Trigger efficiency vs $\log(t_e$ (days)). At low t_e the altLike cadence does better than the bulge cadence which does better than the baseline cadence. However, at high t_e , all three are at 100% trigger efficiency.

Figure 7. Detection efficiency vs $\log(t_e$ (days)) At low t_e the altLike cadence does better than the bulge cadence which does better than the baseline cadence. However, at high t_e , all three are at approximately the same detection efficiency. They are not at 100% due to edge effects.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

One can ask if we will observe enough stars with the LSST in the Galactic bulge region to distinguish between the black hole population and the rest of the objects. By integrating over t_e greater than one year and with an anticipated 10^8 observed stars, there is expected to be approximately 2000 events/5 years due

to black holes and approximately 650 events/5 years by main sequence stars, white dwarfs, and neutron stars combined. So for a 10 year survey, there is expected to be approximately 5300 ± 218 events total to three sigma confidence and approximately 1300 ± 108 events for all components besides black holes to three sigma confidence. So we would be able to tell the scenarios with and without LIGO black holes apart. The detection efficiency of events at high Einstein crossing times by main sequence stars may decrease due to their high luminosity suppressing the apparent amplification of the events. This will further exaggerate the difference between the black hole and main sequence curves, making it easier to detect the difference in populations. Since the relevant events are at such high Einstein crossing times, we would be able to observe them regardless of cadence.

A major assumption in this analysis is that the velocity distribution for these objects is determined and the same for all components. Since high mass objects and slow objects cause the same microlensing effect, it is important to determine the velocity precisely. One way this can be done is through observations with Gaia data. One could also determine the velocity of each microlensing object using outside satellites including the upcoming Wide Field Infrared Survey Telescope (WFIRST) or a small satellite dedicated to microlensing. Finally, for events with a long duration, one could determine the velocity via microlensing parallax using Earth's parallax as it moves around the Sun, which is relatively easy to measure.

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